

SiC_p/Al METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES USING ATOMIZATION AND CO-DEPOSITION

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ABSTRACT

In the process of particulate reinforced metal matrix composites the injection of solid particulate into the molten metal is computed. By considering the resistance for injection of a particulate as comprising drag, surface, and buoyancy, a criterion has been derived. For the implant of a particulate there is a minimum impinge velocity of a particulate onto melt, and larger diameter of particulate, improvement in the wetting conditions, increase of kinetic energy of particulate favor initiation of particulate transfer to melt.

Keywords: Metal Matrix Composite, Atomization and Co-Deposition, and SiC Particulates.

1. INTRODUCTION

Particulate reinforced metal matrix composites have been produced by numerous techniques^[1]. Among the various synthesis techniques spray atomization and co-deposition offers a potentially attractive route as a result of a number of factors. First, the technology retains most of the advantages of the powder route while eliminating some of its major disadvantages. Second, spray atomized and deposited materials have been reported to exhibit some of the characteristics associated with rapid solidification. Third, spray atom-

ization and co-deposition processes have the potential of being utilized for near net shape manufacturing of difficult to form materials, such as intermetallics. The process, is essentially a technique for the conversion of molten metal, through gas atomization, to a particulate spray which impinges directly on a collector to form a deposit for direct use or subsequent operations. Therefore, it is very necessary to study the complex fluid, thermodynamics and solidification phenomena involved in this processes. The paper deals with the transfer of particulates into metal matrix during the process.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The spray atomization and co-deposition apparatus is shown in Figure 1(a). The molten aluminium alloy is atomized into a fine dispersion by inert gas jets and the SiC strengthening phases are injected into the spray with special jets at the same time. The solidification and the thickness of the liquid film are controlled by the water cooling system. The injection velocity and fraction volume of SiC strengthening phase are regulated by specially designed fluidized bed as shown in Figure 1(b). The matrix metal is 6061 aluminium alloy, and the reinforcement is SiC particulates with 5-50um size in diameter.

3. ANALYSIS OF PARTICULATE IMPLANT

The spray atomization and co-deposition includes atomization of melt, mixture of particulates and melt drops, entrance of particulates, entrapment by melt film, and solidification. Some aspects have been studied^[2].

Figure 1(a). Schematic diagram of experimental apparatus

(b). Fluidized bed for transfer of particulate powder

The implant of particulates is schematically shown in Figure 2. SiC particulates and melt atomized in the atomizer fly onto the co-deposition layer where has a molten metal film in order to obtain compact composites. The transfer of a particulate into the melt will meet three resistances, including drag resistance F_d , surfacial resistance F_s and buoyance F_b .

The drag resistance can be calculated as following^[3]

$$F_d = -k s \rho_M \frac{(u)^2}{2} \tag{1}$$

where k is a factor of the resistance and equal to 1.3, s is the maximum cross section (projection surface). ρ_M is density of molten metal and u is motion velocity of particulate in melt.

The surfacial resistance can be calculated as following

$$F_s = dW_s / dh \tag{2}$$

The increment of surfacial energy

$$dw = \sigma_{mp} ds \tag{3}$$

the change of surfacial area of moving particulate in melt

$$ds = 2\pi r dh$$

Where h is the travel distance of particulate in melt, r is the radius of particulate, and by

Figure 2. Schematic illustration of the implant of particulates

the Young-Dupre equation

$$\sigma_{mp} = \sigma_{ps} - \sigma_{ms} \cos \theta \quad (4)$$

where θ is the contact angle, σ_s are the specific surface energies of subscripted interfaces.

After algebraic computation, we have

$$F_s = 2\pi r \sigma_{mp} \quad (5)$$

The buoyance can be calculated as following

$$F_b = \frac{4}{3} \pi r^3 g (\rho_M - \rho_p) \quad (6)$$

Owing the motion of a particulate in the melt is a retarded motion, we have a following equation

$$m_p \frac{dv}{d\tau} = - (F_d + F_s + F_b) \quad (7)$$

where m_p is mass of particulate, and $m_p = \frac{4}{3} \pi r^3 \rho_p$

After substitution for F_d , F_s and F_b form eqs [1], [5] and [6], leads to

$$\frac{dv}{d\tau} = -\alpha v^2 - \beta \quad (8)$$

where

$$\alpha = \frac{3ks\rho_M}{8\pi r^3 \rho_p}; \quad \beta = \frac{3\sigma}{2r^2 \rho_p} + \frac{3g(\rho_M - \rho_p)}{2\rho_p} \quad (9)$$

After integration of eq. [8], the velocity of a particulate in the melt can be obtained

$$V = \frac{v_1 - \gamma \operatorname{tg}(\alpha \gamma \tau)}{1 + \frac{v_1}{\gamma} \operatorname{tg}(\alpha \gamma \tau)} \quad (10)$$

where $\gamma = \sqrt{\frac{\beta}{\alpha}}$, v_1 is the initial velocity reach to film of a particulate, τ is the moving

time in melt.

Hence

$$h = \int_0^t v d\tau$$

which leads on substitution and rearrangement to

$$h = \frac{1}{\alpha} \ln \frac{\left[\frac{\gamma}{v_1} + \operatorname{tg}(\alpha\gamma\tau) \right] v_1}{\gamma \sqrt{1 + \operatorname{tg}^2(\alpha\gamma\tau)}}$$

In order to trap the particulates impinging into the molten metal. The impinge distance should be greater than and equal to $2r$ while the conditions of solidification front and thermodynamic of the deposition block meet some demands. And suppose $v_2 = 0$, we have

$$\operatorname{tg}(\alpha\gamma\tau) = v_1\gamma$$

replace this into the eq. above, we can get

$$V_1 = \gamma \sqrt{e^{4\alpha\gamma} - 1} \quad (11)$$

replace γ , k , $s = \frac{5}{6}\pi r^2$, σ_{mp} into eq. (11) we have the minimum velocity of a particulate for impinging into molten metal:

$$V_{\min} = 2 \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_{ps} - \sigma_{mg} \cos\theta}{r \cdot \rho_M}} \cdot \sqrt{e^{\frac{1.5\rho_M}{\rho_p}} - 1} \quad (12)$$

4. RESULT AND DISCUSION

The spray and co-deposition process should be regarded as a statistical process where the averages of the parameters involved which vary randomly in time govern overall behaviour of the process. The general analysis has been carried out above which indicates that the velocity of a SiC particulate arrival at the deposition surface should have a critical value. It is important to maintain as high a velocity value as possible since the velocity of SiC particulates is advantageous in impinging them into liquid metal. In order

to obtain quality particulate reinforced SiC/Al composites. Particulates should transfer to liquid metal. There are two ways for this goal. First, the particulates are given as large kinetic energy as possible in the inert gas jets. Second, the critical velocity should be minimized by suitable selected the parameters.

The SiC/Al composite is co-deposited with SiC particulates of 1-50 μm in diameter, but the fine Particulates are hardly to be found, as shown in Figure 3(a). The criterion of a particulate entrance is the impinging velocity at the deposition surface. The velocity is a function of diameter of particulates and of distance from the atomizer, but the extremely short duration of flight makes experimental measurements difficult. A computer simulation^[4] shows the velocity changes are strongly dependent on particulate diameter. Small particulates rapidly accelerate to a maximum velocity, but slow down rapidly as the distance increase. Large particulates also rapidly attain peak velocity, but this velocity changes very little for quite large flight distance.

Since the particulates with small diameter are rapidly decelerated in their motion, it is difficult to give small particulates enough impinging velocity. This effect can found in Figure 3(b).

Figure 3. Microstructures of the co-deposition composites; (a) powder was jetted with lower velocity (b) powder was jetted with higher velocity, (c) particulates were treated wetting agent

In fabrication of fibrous composites improve surface tension and wetting state is a very effective method, it is also a practical way in atomization and co-deposition process as shown in eq. [12]. Particulates coated with metallic material are used in this study as shown in Figure 3(c). These particulates can be reach their criterion of impinging velocity easily. The Young-Dupre equation is assumed to apply at interphase boundaries at every stage during the process of particulate transfer. Therefore, it is very effective method to decrease the contact angle and the interfacial force between melt and particulate.

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper an analysis is presented for the transfer of particulates across a gas-liquid interface to the matrix of SiC/Al composites. The analysis also proposes a criterion for transfer of particulates into a melt. According to the criterion, the impinging velocity of a particulate to the melt is the determinant, and larger particulates, small interface force between melt and particulate, larger dynamic energy in jets favor initiation of the transfer.

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